

eMOTIONAL Cities

Mapping the cities through the senses
of those who make them

DELIVERABLE 3.3

Description of the SDIs I

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Executive Summary

This deliverable provides a description of the Spatial Data Infrastructure (SDI), including configuration details and how it can be accessed and used in the context of the eMOTIONAL Cities project. The SDI publishes a set of public endpoints, which are detailed in this document.

The document starts with an introduction, followed by a presentation of the data showcased in the examples. The description of the SDI is divided into three different sections, which correspond to the different steps of the data and metadata pipeline:

- Data and metadata ingestion: explains how the data can be ingested into the SDI.
- Data publishing: explains how the SDI can be configured to publish the data using the selected standards.
- Using the SDI: explains how the published data can be accessed/used using different tools.

The document is wrapped up with some conclusions, which present some thoughts regarding the current work and future developments.

Introduction

The main objective of the eMOTIONAL Cities project is to identify potential mechanisms through which the natural and built environment shapes the human emotional and cognitive neural systems, which ultimately underlie the well-being of individuals living in urban contexts¹.

In the data interviews performed as part of the requirements gathered for the Data Management Plan (D3.1²) we learned that a great proportion of the data which is expected to be generated and shared by the consortium both internally and externally is geospatial, i.e., it has a location tag associated with it. The purpose of the SDI is to store, manage and publish these geospatial data, in order to make the information FAIR: Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable.

¹ <https://emotionalcities-h2020.eu/about/>

² Data Management Plan (DMP) I

https://emotionalcities-h2020.eu/wp-content/uploads/2022/02/eMC_2021.08_D3.1_Data_Management_Plan.pdf

Deliverable 3.2 (D3.2³) describes the technical aspects of the SDI, including the architecture, technology stack and how to deploy it. This deliverable instead focuses on the user experience, describing how stakeholders can ingest data into the SDI and access it from various tools. In order to make this description more expressive, we will focus on a use case of one of the SDI stakeholders and show the complete process of how the data and accompanying metadata can be ingested and then used from the SDI. At the current state of the art, creating an SDI based solely on Open Geospatial Consortium (OGC) API standards still has some limitations [1]. This has led us to include in our architecture components that publish data using first-generation OGC standards (e.g.: WMS, WMTS, WFS), as well as standards from the OGC API family (e.g.: OGC API Features, OGC API Tiles, OGC API Records) [2]. We called the first set “legacy” standards and the second set “modern” standards. A complete description of the reasons for supporting these two stacks, as well as details about their implementation, is available in D3.2. In the current deliverable, we present detailed instructions for configuring and using the “legacy” and “modern” stacks.

At this stage, we have taken the decision to ingest all the datasets generated during this project in a single SDI. The multi-service architecture and the flexibility of the underlying tools (see D3.2) enable us to support a variety of options, which can accommodate the different use cases in a single deployment. The flexibility of the cloud environment also enables us to scale instances, up to a certain point, in order to meet storage and processing demands. If we find out during the project that we can no longer accommodate all the datasets in the same instance, we will have the option to switch to multiple deployments in a straightforward manner, due to all the automation in place.

³ Architecture definition and code for the generic SDI
https://emotionalcities-h2020.eu/wp-content/uploads/2022/11/eMC_2022.08_D3.2_Architecture_definition_and_code_for_the_generic_SDI.pdf

1. Use case data

The use case that we describe in this document concerns data from the research developed in WP4, by Cambridge University. It consists of vector datasets that describe the distribution of different variables in the city of London (e.g.: physical health, wellbeing outcomes, physical environment, health behaviours). We will focus on a dataset which describes the annual average concentration of pm2.5.

Figure 1 - Example of one of the datasets provided by Cambridge University: map of the annual average concentration of pm2.5 in London (2019).

2. Data and metadata ingestion

Considering the different characteristics of the datasets and the different levels of SDI literacy within the consortium, we opted to establish a separate environment for data ingestion, which allows us to have full control over the information that enters the SDI. We also tried to make the process as easy as possible for the user, even if that meant that sometimes we had to process the data before ingesting it into the SDI.

In Figure 2, we show the entry points for submitting data and metadata into the SDI: the data lake and the Google form.

Figure 2 - Entry points for submitting data and metadata into the SDI.

The data lake is a data format agnostic storage, where users can store ingest-ready files. The files can be in different formats, but they must already be structured in order to relate features of interest with spatial coordinates, in practice the point or area to which they refer. The formats supported are those that emerged during the interviews with the project partners, but it cannot be excluded that new formats could emerge during the project. These are the formats that were uploaded to the data lake:

- CSV
- ESRI Geodatabase
- GeoJSON
- GeoPackage

Technology-wise, the data lake is an S3 bucket hosted on Amazon Web Services' (AWS) Simple Storage Service (S3) [3]. Each partner was assigned a specific folder on the bucket, which is safeguarded by identity and permission control.

<input type="checkbox"/>	Nome	Tipo
<input type="checkbox"/>	📁 camb/	Cartella
<input type="checkbox"/>	📁 clima/	Cartella
<input type="checkbox"/>	📁 fmul/	Cartella
<input type="checkbox"/>	📁 igot/	Cartella
<input type="checkbox"/>	📁 msu/	Cartella
<input type="checkbox"/>	📁 nrg/	Cartella
<input type="checkbox"/>	📁 slab/	Cartella
<input type="checkbox"/>	📁 tt/	Cartella
<input type="checkbox"/>	📁 utartu/	Cartella

Figure 3 - Structure of the eMOTIONAL Cities data lake, on AWS S3.

Each partner is responsible for the sensitive data it processes for its own experiments or data collection, and, at the moment of sharing it, has the responsibility of removing or masking any sensitive information properly. Any exceptions to this must be properly reported so that proper precautions can be taken.

We have created detailed instructions on how to access the data lake⁴ and organized a workshop during the 2nd Scientific meeting of the project (July, 2022), which explained, among other things, how to ingest data into the data lake⁵.

Each dataset submission should be accompanied by a matching metadata submission, a fundamental condition for data sharing according to FAIR principles. In order to ease the process of submitting metadata we have created a Google form⁶, where the owner of the dataset indicates useful information for the ingestion process, selects the appropriate services and formats and creates the metadata record.

⁴ Instructions for sharing data, using AWS S3
<https://github.com/emotional-cities/data-share>

⁵ Workshop for the eMOTIONAL Cities 2nd Business Meeting, in Estonia
<https://github.com/emotional-cities/byteroad-workshop>

⁶ Dataset metadata submission form
https://docs.google.com/forms/d/e/1FAIpQLScnqcDkmJrsSwgvQdoVknPdIANdMaw7-Pt9x0ziGwY9Is_2Zg/viewform

In Table 1, we show the fields present in this form. These fields are aligned using the atomic unit of information of the Spatial-Temporal Asset Catalog (STAC) and OGC API Records [4].

Field	Description	Mandatory
Title	A title for the dataset and metadata record	Yes
Description	Description of the dataset	Yes
Dataset location	In which folder of the data lake the dataset is located	Yes
SDI Services	Through which services it will have to be published OGC API Features OGC API Tiles WMS WFS	Yes
Owners of the dataset	The project partner owner of the dataset	Yes
Contact points	The contact points to indicate in the metadata record	Yes
Sensitive information	Indicates whether the record contains sensitive information	Yes
Publicly available	Indicates whether the record could be published without restrictions	Yes
Licence information	The licence associated with the dataset (default Creative Commons (CC BY 4.0))	Yes
Geometry field	The name of the geometry field	Yes
Created	Creation date	Yes
Updated	Last update date	
Keywords	The topic or topics of the resource. Typically represented using keywords, tags, key phrases, or classification codes. Recommended best practice is to use a controlled vocabulary (please indicate keyword codespace if used).	
Themes	A knowledge organization system is used to classify the resource. A resolvable URI must be used for each entity/concept identifier. One line per entity/concept. (eg. Check https://www.eionet.europa.eu/gemet/en/groups/)	
Notes	Extra information useful for dataset publishing or metadata	
Data Collection Tool	Instrument used to collect data	
Bounding Box	The area to which the dataset refers can be deduced from the dataset itself (default). Otherwise, it can be indicated which area of the map has to be referred to.	

Table 1 - List of collected metadata fields.

Data publishing

2.1 The modern stack

Based on the requirements expressed in the data surveys and the type of data which was submitted (e.g.: at this time, only vector data), we have selected the OGC API Features [5], OGC API Tiles [6] and OGC API Records [7] standards/draft standards for publication. For the purpose of publishing data and metadata using these standards, we have selected pygeoapi [8].

pygeoapi is a Python-based implementation of the OGC API suite of standards. It is an open-source server implementation that provides a simple way to publish geospatial data over the web using standard protocols like HTTP and JSON and is one of the reference implementations for the development of OGC API specifications.

pygeoapi can be configured to publish data from different data providers. Our SDI it's configured with the Elasticsearch backend storage, where the assets are stored as GeoJSON.

For the uploading, the datasets were converted to GeoJSON and placed in a folder which the SDI could access. Then pygeoapi was configured to publish this data. In Figure 3, we show a snippet of the pygeoapi configuration, which publishes the Annual mean PM2.5 dataset. As we can see in lines 390 and 394, Elasticsearch is used as a backend, both for serving the features as OGC API Features (OAF) and the vector tiles as OGC API Tiles (OAT).

```

366
367 hex350_grid_pm25_2019:
368   type: collection
369   title: Annual mean PM2.5 based on output areas average concentrations in London.
370   description: Maps of physical environment &#11088;&#11088;&#11088;
371   keywords:
372     - London
373     - eMOTIONAL Cities
374     - Maps of physical environment
375     - Health determinates
376   links:
377     - type: text/html
378       rel: canonical
379       title: metadata
380       # TODO: replace this later
381       href: https://emotional.byteroad.net/collections/ec_catalog/items/6c22e1572c4f4a44121d6e50cf6141
382       hreflang: en-US
383   extents:
384     spatial:
385       bbox: [-0.2607653545419580, 51.4096281337334560, 0.1267201969466480, 51.5800306780284501]
386       crs: http://www.opengis.net/def/crs/OGC/1.3/CRS84
387   providers:
388     - type: feature
389       name: Elasticsearch
390       data: http://elastic_search:9200/hex350_grid_pm25_2019
391       id_field: fid
392     - type: tile
393       name: MVT
394       data: http://elastic_search:9200/hex350_grid_pm25_2019/_mvt/geometry/{z}/{x}/{y}?grid_precision=0
395   options:
396     metadata_format: raw # default | tilejson
397     zoom:
398       min: 0
399       max: 15
400     schemes:
401       - WorldCRS84Quad
402   format:
403     name: pbf
404     mimetype: application/vnd.mapbox-vector-tile
405

```

Figure 4 - Configuration of the annual mean PM2.5 dataset in pygeoapi.

2.2 The legacy stack

In order to make the datasets usable by popular GIS clients, such as QGIS and Mapstore, we have published them in GeoServer using well-known, first-generation OGC standards (e.g.: WMS, WMTS and WFS). GeoServer [9] is one of the most popular GIS servers, especially among open-source solutions. It is capable of loading GIS data from a variety of data sources, from geospatial databases to file formats [10].

Specifically for the project and the formats identified for loading the data, the Shapefile, GeoJSON and GeoPackage formats will be loaded directly from the filesystem, while the CSV will be converted into a table to be loaded into the PostGIS database (included into the SDI).

Figure 5 - Data Source configuration options in Geoserver.

Starting from a configured data source (see Figure 6), it is possible to configure one or more layers in GeoServer, using the layer wizard.

Edit Layer

Edit layer data and publishing

camb:hex350_grid_pm25_2019

Configure the resource and publishing information for the current layer

Edit Layer

Basic Resource Info

Nome: hex350_grid_pm25_2019

Native Name: Hex250_grid_pm25_2019

Nome

hex350_grid_pm25_2019

Abilitato

Advertised

Titolo i18n

hex350_grid_pm25_2019

Abstract i18n

Keywords

Current Keywords

New Keyword

Vocabolario

Figure 6 - Configuring a layer in Geoserver.

Layers can be organized in different workspaces, to facilitate their management. The current strategy of the project is to create a workspace for each project partner.

Some project datasets have associated styles, to improve the display of information otherwise encapsulated in the various features (see Figure 7). Layer styling is a feature which is currently available only on the legacy stack. With styles, it is possible to tell the server how the different layers should be displayed.

Figure 7 - Layer with associated style.

GeoServer features an SLD (Styled Layer Descriptor) editor [11]. A Styled Layer Descriptor is an XML schema specified by the Open Geospatial Consortium for describing the appearance of map layers. It is capable of describing the rendering of vector and raster data. A typical use of SLDs is to instruct a Web Map Service on how to render a specific layer.

Figure 8 - The style editor in GeoServer.

It is possible to associate a single SLD with one or more layers.

3. Using the SDI

3.1 The modern stack

The landing page of the SDI can be accessed through this URL:

<https://emotional.byteroad.net/>

As with every endpoint, this content is available both as JSON (for machines) and HTML (for humans), via content negotiation [12].

The screenshot shows the landing page of the pygeoapi eMOTIONAL Cities instance. The page includes a navigation bar with 'Home' and 'json jsonld' links. The main content area features the title 'pygeoapi eMOTIONAL Cities instance' and a description: 'Provides an API to eMOTIONAL Cities geospatial data'. Below this, there are several sections: 'Terms of service' with a link to the Creative Commons license, 'Collections' with a link to view collections, 'API Definition' with links to Swagger UI and OpenAPI Document, and 'Conformance' with a link to view conformance classes. On the right side, there is a 'Provider' section for ByteRoad and a 'Contact point' section with details like address, email, telephone, and contact instructions.

Figure 9 - HTML representation of the landing page of the SDI.

From there, it is possible to navigate to the different URLs that follow the OGC API standard.

On the `/api` endpoint, we can find an OpenAPI definition [13], which can be inspected by developers, who want to study this API (see Figure 10).

The screenshot shows a list of API endpoints for the 'hex350_grid_pm25_2019' collection. Each endpoint is listed with its method (GET) and a brief description of the data it returns. The endpoints include metadata, items, items by feature ID, queryables, tiles, and tiles with matrix set ID, matrix, row, and column.

Figure 10 - Subset of the swagger page of the SDI, which shows the different endpoints for the annual mean PM2.5 dataset.

On the /collections endpoint, we can find a list of all the collections (e.g.: datasets) available on this instance (see figure 11).

Name	Type	Description
Prevalence rates of cardiovascular diseases in London.	feature	Maps of physical health ★★★
Prevalence rates of obesity in London.	feature	Maps of physical health ★★★
Prevalence rates of depression in London.	feature	Maps of wellbeing outcomes ★★★
Prevalence rates of mental health issues in London.	feature	Maps of wellbeing outcomes ★★★
Prevalence rates of dementia in London.	feature	Maps of wellbeing outcomes ★★★
Proportion of population with access to public open space in London.	feature	Maps of physical environment ★★★
Normalized difference vegetation index (NDVI) in London.	feature	Maps of physical environment ★★★
Annual mean PM2.5 based on output areas average concentrations in London.	feature	Maps of physical environment ★★★
Annual mean PM10 based on output areas average concentrations in London.	feature	Maps of physical environment ★★★
Annual mean NO2 concentration in London.	feature	Maps of physical environment ★★★
Annual average noise levels of rail noise in London.	feature	Maps of physical environment ★★★
Risk of flooding from rivers and seas in London.	feature	Maps of physical environment ★★★
Major summer heat spots in London.	feature	Maps of physical environment ★★★
Cycling routes density map in London.	feature	Maps of physical environment ★★★
Land use diversity in London.	feature	Maps of physical environment ★★★

Figure 11 - List of collections available on the SDI.

By clicking on one of the collections, we navigate to the collection page, where more information about this collection is provided. Here, we can also find the links to access this collection with different formats; in this case: OAF and OAT.

emotional.byteroad.net/collections/hex350_grid_pm25_2019

pygeoapi Contact

Home / Collections / Annual mean PM2.5... json |sonid

Annual mean PM2.5 based on output areas average concentrations in London.

Maps of physical environment ⭐⭐⭐

London eMOTIONAL CITIES Maps of physical environment Health determinants

Browse

- Browse through the items of "Annual mean PM2.5 based on output areas average concentrations in London."

Queryable

- Display Queryables of "Annual mean PM2.5 based on output areas average concentrations in London."

Tiles

- Display Tiles of "Annual mean PM2.5 based on output areas average concentrations in London."

Figure 12 - Detailed collection endpoint for annual mean PM2.5 dataset.

Figure 13 shows the endpoints for one collection published as OAF, and for a single feature of this collection.

Figure 13 - Endpoint for retrieving the items of the annual mean PM2.5 dataset as features.

Figure 14 shows the HTML representation of the endpoint for OAT.

Figure 14 - Endpoint for retrieving the items of the annual mean PM2.5 dataset as tiles.

The metadata was published using the OGC API Records draft standard. The endpoint for the catalog is also exposed in the /collections endpoint, featuring type "record". By clicking it, we can access the eMOTIONAL Cities Metadata catalog.

Figure 15 - Endpoint for accessing the eMOTIONAL Cities Metadata Catalog.

From the catalog page, we can browse through the different records (one per dataset) and inspect one particular record (figure 16). Each metadata record contains relevant information about the dataset, such as language, description or contact point, as well as links for the associated data (see Table 1).

Figure 16 - List of metadata records in the catalog (left) and detail of a single record (right).

The value of having data in the SDI lies in the ability to be able to use it from different tools, in particular those that the users are familiar with. In the next sections, we show how to use data from the SDI using different tools. These examples are part of a wider pool of tools (both open source and proprietary), which is only likely to grow with time. The benefit of using standards is to be able to use all the tools that support those standards.

3.1.1 QGIS

QGIS [14] (Quantum Geographic Information System) is a free and open-source cross-platform software that is used for the creation, editing, visualization, and analysis of geospatial data. It is an essential tool in our GIS infrastructure as it allows users to manipulate and analyze project data exposed by server-side endpoints. QGIS is a cross-platform software that can run on Windows, macOS, and Linux operating systems.

One of the key strengths of QGIS is its ability to perform complex spatial analysis. It has a vast range of spatial analysis tools that can be used to perform operations such as buffer creation, overlay analysis, and spatial queries. This functionality is particularly useful for professionals working in the fields of urban planning, environmental management, and natural resource management.

QGIS also allows for the integration of different data sources, making it possible to combine data from multiple sources to create comprehensive and accurate geospatial datasets.

Among many others, QGIS has native support for OAF as a vector layer. It is possible to pull an OAF connection, either through the top menu (Layer->Add Layer->Add WFS Layer) or by clicking “WFS/OGC API Features” and then “New Connection...” in the browser on the left-hand side panel (see Figure 11).

Figure 17 - Creating an OAF in QGIS, using the browser.

This will open a menu with some configuration details. The URL should be filled with the URL of the landing page of the SDI: <https://emotional.byteroad.net/> (Figure 18).

Figure 18 - Filling the OAF configuration details.

After pressing “ok”, a new entry will be added to the browser with the name of the connection. The collections (e.g.: layers) available on the SDI, will be listed under the connection (Figure 19).

Figure 19 - List of collections available on the OAF connection.

By double-clicking a connection, it will be added to the map (see Figure 20).

Figure 20 - OAF collection in QGIS.

Although the OAT standard is not natively supported in QGIS, it is possible to pull an OAT collection using the Vector Tiles Layer and customizing a generic connection to match the standard (see Figure 21).

Figure 21 - Creating an OAT connection in QGIS.

Clicking on “New Generic Connection...” will open a dialog to configure the connection details (see Figure 17). The URL should point to the endpoint of the collection in OAT, followed by “/{z}/{x}/{y}?f=mvt”. For instance

https://emotional.byteroad.net/collections/hex350_grid_pm25_2019/tiles/WorldCRS84Quad/{z}/{x}/{y}?f=mvt

Figure 22 - Filling the OAT configuration details.

After adding the connection, the collection should appear in the browser, under the “Vector Tiles” entry (see Figure 23).

Right-clicking the collection will add it to QGIS (see Figure 24).

Figure 23 - OAT collection on the browser.

Figure 24 - OAT collection in QGIS.

QGIS provides native support to OGC API records through its core plugin, metasearch [15].

In order to add a catalog connection, go to the top-level menu and select “web->Metasearch”. To add the configuration, go to the “Services” tab and choose “New”. Then fill in the relevant values (see Figure 25):

- In this case, the URL should be the URL of the catalog (not the landing page!)
- In the options, select “OGC API Records”.

Figure 25 - Adding a catalog/OGC API records connection in Metasearch.

After adding the connection, you can click “Service info” to see more information about the service (e.g.: service metadata). Then you can proceed to the “Search” tab, where you can browse through the records and filter them by keyword or bounding box (See Figure 26). Clicking on a record will display information about the record, by default in HTML.

Figure 26 - Pulling the records from an OGC API Records Catalog in Metasearch.

3.1.2 Leaflet

Leaflet [16] is an open-source JavaScript library for creating interactive maps on the web. It provides an easy-to-use API for developers to add various map-related functionalities to their web applications. Leaflet can be used to create a wide range of maps, from simple static maps to complex, dynamic maps with a lot of interactivity.

Although OAT is not supported natively in Leaflet, it is possible to pull an OAT collection in Leaflet, by using the vectorGrid.protobuf layer. For instance, the “hex350_grid_pm25_2019” collection can be added using the following code:

```
map.addLayer(new L.vectorGrid.protobuf(
  'https://emotional.byteroad.net/collections/hex350_grid_pm25_2019/tiles/WorldCRS84Quad/{z}/{x}/{y}
  ?f=mvt', { rendererFactory: L.canvas.tile }));
```


Figure 27 - OAT collection in Leaflet.

The complete HTML/JavaScript code for the interactive map shown in Figure 20, is listed in the Annex (Listing 1).

Currently, OAF is not supported in Leaflet. However, since OAF outputs features in GeoJSON, it is possible to add an OAF collection by launching an asynchronous call to read the features and then passing them directly to L.geoJSON.

```
async function pull_oat() {
  let url = 'https://emotional.byteroad.net/collections/hex350_grid_pm25_2019/items?limit=10000';
  const response = await fetch(url)
  const shape_obj = await response.json();
  console.log(shape_obj);
  return shape_obj;
}
pull_oat().then(L.geoJson).then(map.addLayer.bind(map));
```


allows querying any catalog which supports the standard and previewing metadata, along with associated data. In addition, it also offers React components, which can be reused by developers in other applications. The source code is available on GitHub [24] with an MIT License, and a hosted version is available here:

<https://luoghi-indomiti.github.io/a-gis-full-of-records/>

The entry point of the application allows configuring the URL of the landing page (see Figure 24). The application supports different OGC API standards (e.g.: features, and records).

Figure 29 - Entry page of the catalog application.

Figure 30 - Navigating through the record collection.

If we select a record collection (e.g.: catalog), the next page will let us browse through the records and preview a particular record (as JSON).

Check this OGC API

```

Back to items
{
  "root": {
    "temporal": {
      "interval": int 2019
      "trs": string "http://www.opengis.net/def/uom/ISO-8601/0/Gregorian"
    }
    "@version": string "1"
    "properties": {
      "language": string "en"
      "contactPoint": {
        "institution": string "University of Cambridge"
      }
      "extent": {
        "spatial": {
          "bbox": [
            0 : float -1.11
            1 : float 51.06
            2 : float 0.87
            3 : float 51.9
          ]
        }
        "crs": string "http://www.opengis.net/def/crs/OGC/1.3/CRS84"
      }
    }
  }
}

```

Figure 31 - Previewing a record.

3.2 The legacy stack

The Geoserver GUI is available at:

<https://emotional.byteroad.net/geoserver>

From the WMS, WFS and WMTS endpoints of GeoServer it is possible to explore the catalog of layers configured in the server like done with collections in OGC APIs.

Supported endpoints are:

Service	Endpoint
WMS	https://emotional.byteroad.net/geoserver/wms
WMTS	https://emotional.byteroad.net/geoserver/gwc/service/wmts
WFS	https://emotional.byteroad.net/geoserver/wfs

Table 2 - List of OGC legacy web services endpoints in GeoServer.

3.2.1 QGIS

All the layers made available through GeoServer services can be easily consumed via QGIS, In a similar way to what was done with the OGC API endpoints, from the dedicated Browser section:

Figure 32 - QGIS Browser panel

For each service, it's necessary to select the proper type and to indicate the proper GeoServer's endpoint:

Figure 33 - The form for WMS endpoint configuration.

After saving, it will be possible to browse through the available layers in GeoServer (Figure 34) and add them to the map (Figure 35).

Figure 34 - The eMOTIONAL Cities WMS layers configured in QGIS browser.

Figure 35 - A WMS layer visualized in the in QGIS workspace map.

3.2.2 MapStore

Another possible alternative to using the services of GeoServer is via a WebGIS, like MapStore [18]. MapStore is a web-based GIS application that uses OGC OWS standards to allow users to create, manage, and share maps and data over the web. It is designed to be easily integrable with GeoServer services.

MapStore is one of the tools included in the eMOTIONAL Cities SDI, and it is available at the URL:

<https://emotional.byteroad.net/mapstore>

Figure 36 - MapStore home page.

Each map configured in Mapstore contains a table of contents with already configured layers, that is possible to visualize on the main map, and some basic manipulation.

Figure 37 - The annual average concentration of pm2.5 in the city of London visualized in MapStore.

Similarly to QGIS, it's possible to load more layers from different sources to customize the loaded map and create thematic visualizations. To do that it's necessary to configure a new catalog, from the main menu:

Figure 38 - The MapStore main menu.

In this example, we configured the eMOTIONAL Cities WMS endpoint. It's possible to add any public endpoint exposing WMS, WMTS, WFS, CSW and TMS:

Figure 39 - The catalog configuration endpoint.

Service Catalog

eMOTIONAL Cities WMS

text to search...

Search

- Preview Not Available Proportion of population with access to public open space in Lo...
Maps of physical environment
camb:hex250_grid_access2openspace
- Preview Not Available Map of ratio of active people in Inner London
Maps of health behaviours
camb:hex250_grid_active2020
- Preview Not Available Map of the ratio of elder people in London
Maps of socioeconomic groups

« < 1 2 3 4 5 > »

Results 1-4 of 20

Figure 40 - WMS layers loaded in the catalog panel.

4. Conclusions

Both the OGC API standards and the technologies that support these standards have evolved since we started designing the SDI. Currently, it is not only possible to publish data as features and tiles and metadata, but also to consume these data from a myriad of tools, some of them quite popular within the GIS, data science and full stack development communities. Although we focused our description on Free and Open Source tools, proprietary tools such as ArcGIS also support these standards, which gives a convenient pool of options for SDI users. For the cases where the tools do not support these standards, the legacy stack is always a safe choice, and this is why we use it as a fallback. Our main goal is to make users' lives easy, by letting them use their favourite tools, without too much hassle to learn how to use the data from the SDI.

However, this document does not represent the final word on the topic, and it is clear that user feedback will be essential to inform future developments. Therefore, we do not rule out the possibility of further evolutions to the infrastructure, based on the needs and priorities of the project partners. Ultimately, the success of a spatial data infrastructure for neuroscience research data will depend on ongoing engagement and collaboration between researchers, data managers, and other stakeholders, as well as a commitment to continuous improvement and innovation.

5. References

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6. Annex

```
<html>

<head><title>OGC API - Tiles exercise</title></head>

<body>

<div id="map" style="width:100vw;height:100vh;"></div>

<link rel="stylesheet" href="https://unpkg.com/leaflet@1.0.3/dist/leaflet.css"/>

<script type="text/javascript" src="https://unpkg.com/leaflet@1.3.1/dist/leaflet.js"></script>

<script type="text/javascript" src="https://unpkg.com/leaflet.vectorgrid@1.2.0"></script>

<script>

map = L.map('map').setView({ lng: -0.08, lat: 51.509 }, 11);

map.addLayer(

  new L.tileLayer('https://stamen-tiles-{s}.a.ssl.fastly.net/watercolor/{z}/{x}/{y}.{ext}', {

    attribution: 'Map tiles by <a href="https://stamen.com">Stamen Design</a>, <a

href="https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/3.0">CC BY 3.0</a> &mdash; Map data &copy; <a

href="https://www.openstreetmap.org/copyright">OpenStreetMap</a> contributors',

    subdomains: 'abcd',

    minZoom: 1,

    maxZoom: 16,

    ext: 'jpg'

  });

map.addLayer(new L.vectorGrid.protobuf(
```

Listing 1 - Source code from an example of using OGC API Features with Leaflet

```
'https://emotional.byteroad.net/collections/hex350_grid_pm25_2019/tiles/WorldCRS84Quad/{z}/{x}/{y}
?f=mvt',
  { rendererFactory: L.canvas.tile });
</script>
</body>
</html>

async function pull_oat() {
  let url = 'https://emotional.byteroad.net/collections/hex350_grid_pm25_2019/items?limit=10000';
  const response = await fetch(url)
  const shape_obj = await response.json();
  console.log(shape_obj);
  return shape_obj;
}

pull_oat().then(L.geoJson).then(map.addLayer.bind(map));
```

Listing 2 - Source code from an example of using OGC API Tiles with Leaflet

eMOTIONAL Cities

Mapping the cities through the senses
of those who make them